

THE USE OF MOLECULAR DOCKING TO DETERMINE RECEPTOR AND LIGAND INTERACTIONS IN ANTICANCER STUDIES

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Cancer is a global health problem that causes 10 million deaths in 2020 (Ferlay et al., 2020) so research to find anticancer drugs continues to be carried out. Cancer treatments such as chemotherapy and surgery often have detrimental effects on patients. Patients who receive a combination of chemotherapy drugs during cancer treatment experience hair loss, changes in nail color, changes in taste, decreased appetite, nausea, and neurological disorders (Saini *et al.*, 2015). Along with technological developments, research on anticancer compounds from natural sources provides new hope for finding anticancer drugs with high cytotoxicity but only small side effects. Putri et al. (2022) found that soursop leaf extract could induce apoptosis in HeLa cervical cancer cells. Another research by Kamilia (2021) identified flavonoid compounds from the methanol fraction of Rimau betel leaves and it was found that these flavonoid compounds had very high cytotoxicity in the Brine Shrimp Lethal Test (BSLT). From several studies that have been carried out, it can be seen that compounds that play an anticancer role can only be identified at the compound group level. To find out the types of compounds that play a role and their interactions with cancer cells, further analysis is needed. There are many types of advanced analysis, some examples are LC-MS (Liquid Chromatography, Mass Spectrometry) and molecular docking methods. If anticancer studies are equipped with further tests so that the compounds obtained are in more detail, then this can contribute and be of significant benefit to the development of studies in the field of anticancer drug development.

According to Morris et al. (2008), Molecular docking is such a structure-based drug design method that simulates the molecular interaction and predicts the binding mode and affinity between receptors and ligands. In recent years, this technology has been widely used in drug design research field. Approaches using computational technology such as molecular docking, pharmacological analysis, and so on can increase the ability to analyze active compounds in plants or other natural materials which are used to design and develop more effective cancer drugs (Samadarsi et al., 2022). To perform molecular docking, primarily two types of approaches are used. One of the approaches employs computer simulations, in which energy profiling is estimated for ligand-target docked conformer. Whereas, second approach utilizes a technique that calculates surfaces complementarity between ligand and target (Mukesh et al., 2011). There are various kinds of molecular docking procedures involving either ligand/target flexible or rigid based upon the objectives of docking simulations (Guedes et al., 2014). Specifically, these may be Flexible ligand docking, which incorporates target as rigid molecule. This is the most commonly used in docking. Rigid body docking, where both the target and ligand molecules are kept as rigid molecules. Flexible docking that involves both interacting molecules are flexible (Agarwal et al., 2016). In addition, the emergence of the reverse molecular docking technology could significantly improve the drug target predictive capacity and understand the related molecular mechanism for drug design (Fan et al., 2019). According Ruiz et al. (2021), In reverse docking, the ability of one or a few compounds to bind a large dataset of proteins is evaluated *in silico*. This strategy is useful for identifying molecular targets of orphan bioactive compounds, proposing new molecular mechanisms, finding alternative indications of drugs, or predicting drug toxicity. The reverse docking technique identifies the novel targets by assigning a single small-molecule ligand as the probe to dock with multiple receptors to discover potential binding cavities. In this way, the potential targets of drug can be predicted (Fan et al., 2019).

There are various natural resources that have potential for research regarding the discovery and development of anticancer drugs. Wahyuni et al. (2011) found that *Garcinia cowa* Roxb leaf extract had cytotoxic activity against T47D breast cancer cells. The results of this research will be more accurate if it is added with further tests such as LC-MS or GC-MS and followed by in-silico tests so that substances that are cytotoxic and how they interact with the receptors on T47D cancer cells can be known. In research by Nuryady et al. (2022), molecular docking results reveal that the lucifensin compound has the potential to be an antimicrobial agent in gram-positive bacteria. The effectiveness of a substance on receptors related to certain pathways in the body can be determined through molecular docking. According to Daniel et al. (2018), the bond energy between protein-ligands plays an important role in biological processes in the body, some of which are immune responses, signal transduction, and cell regulation. Pharmacokinetics prediction of a compound needs to be seen using computational studies because this method is more cost-effective and more efficient (Kurnia et al., 2023). Bioactive compounds that have been isolated from plants can be said to be lead compounds if they have a good ADME profile (Fadillah, 2024). ADME is the abbreviation of Absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion. ADME-related in silico models are commonly used to provide a fast and preliminary screening of ADME properties before compounds are further investigated in vitro. In addition, predicting the ADME profile of drug candidates before their synthesis, in the early stage of drug discovery, could help in selecting candidates with the less critical ADME profile (Bocci et al., 2017).

According to Santoso et al. (2024), In silico study such as molecular docking has several limitations that should be considered when interpreting its findings. The study relies heavily on computational approaches, particularly virtual screening and molecular docking, which may not accurately predict the actual biological activities of bioactive compounds and interactions of the compounds in a real biological system. The predicted bioactivity, binding affinities, and interactions should be confirmed through rigorous experimental studies, such as in vitro assays and in vivo study. The study predominantly focuses on individual compound interactions with specific proteins. It overlooks potential synergistic or antagonistic effects when compounds are combined, which is a common approach in herbal medicine. Evaluating compound interactions in combination could yield different outcomes than individual assessments. To conquer the limitations of currently established scoring function, novel algorithm needs to be developed. In particular, for protein-ligand docking, induced-fit motions and flexibility of the protein will be implicated in coming years in an order to discover and design new chemotherapeutic agents (Agarwal et al., 2016).

Drug repurposing has been widely used in discovering and developing new drugs for emerging diseases. It reminds signal of the continuing research development. The molecular docking software can help us to find the optimal conformation and orientation according to complementarity and pre-organization with specific algorithm, followed by applying a scoring function to predict the binding affinity and analyze the interactive mode (Fan et al., 2019). The main objective of molecular docking is to attain an optimized docked conformer of both the interacting molecules in furtherance of achieving lessen free energy of the whole system (Agarwal et al., 2015). The use of molecular docking in research related to the discovery and development of cancer drugs is very time and cost efficient, however further tests such as in-vitro and in-silico studies must also be carried out to validate the results obtained from molecular docking assay.

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